

GUIDING COMMITMENT: THE INFLUENCE OF LEADERSHIP STYLE AND JOB SATISFACTION ON ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT AMONG STATE MADRASAH ALIYAH TEACHERS IN WEST SUMATRA

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DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.11392831](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11392831)

Abstract

The importance of understanding the role of organizational commitment in the educational context and emphasizing the relevance of leadership style factors and job satisfaction in shaping this aspect. This research aims to identify and analyze the influence of leadership style and job satisfaction on the organizational commitment of State Madrasah Aliyah (MAN) teachers in West Sumatra. The research method uses a quantitative approach with path analysis using a decomposition model, involving the population of MAN teachers in West Sumatra who have the status of Civil Servants (PNS). Using a proportional random sampling technique, 280 respondents were selected to answer the questionnaire as a data collection instrument. Data analysis was carried out through classical assumption tests, simple linear regression, multiple regression, and hypothesis testing, including path analysis. The research results show that leadership and job satisfaction directly influence organizational commitment, with leadership also having a direct influence on job satisfaction. In addition, job satisfaction also mediates the relationship between leadership and organizational commitment, contributing 20.89% in increasing commitment through teacher job satisfaction of 2.52%.

Keywords: Influence, Leadership, Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment.

INTRODUCTION

The role of teachers is an important strategy in managing education because good education will produce quality human resources which are the main capital for the progress of the nation and state [1]. Teachers have an irreplaceable role in the process of providing effective education [2]. Therefore, the issues and challenges faced by teachers today are important and crucial to discuss.

Madrasah Aliyah Negeri (MAN) has an important role in the Indonesian education system [3; 4], especially in the context of Islamic education at the secondary level [5]. In West Sumatra, MAN is very influential in shaping students' character and knowledge [6; 7]. However, MAN faces major challenges, especially in maintaining the organizational commitment of teachers [8; 9], which is becoming an increasingly urgent issue to address. Organizational commitment is vital to maintaining consistent and sustainable educational quality [10; 11]. The problem of organizational commitment among MAN teachers in West Sumatra is a major concern [12; 13].

Low levels of organizational commitment can cause negative impacts, such as a decrease in the quality of teaching [14], instability of the work environment [15], and low performance of educational institutions [16].

Furthermore, an effective leadership style can create a conducive work environment and encourage a high level of commitment [17], while job satisfaction influences teachers' perceptions of the quality of the work environment and commitment to the organization where they work [18].

The results of research conducted in various regions and at various levels of education in Indonesia show that teacher commitment to organizations is not as expected [19; 20; 21]. From the results of the author's initial observations at several State Madrasah Aliyah (MAN) in West Sumatra, it is indicated that the organizational commitment of MAN teachers tends to be problematic. This can be seen from the fact that there are still teachers who feel forced to carry out their duties.

By understanding how the interaction between leadership style and job satisfaction can shape organizational commitment among MAN teachers [22]. It is hoped that this understanding can provide better insight into effective human resource management strategies in increasing organizational commitment in the educational environment.

Regarding specific aspects of leadership style and job satisfaction that influence organizational commitment, it can contribute to the development of human resource management theory and practice in the education sector. Not only does it have practical relevance for MAN managers in West Sumatra, but it is also important in the academic literature on human resource management and organizations.

Therefore, this research was designed to study more deeply the organizational commitment of MAN teachers in West Sumatra and the factors that influence it. This research can make a significant contribution to understanding the factors that influence organizational commitment in Islamic educational institutions in Indonesia, as well as provide a strong foundation for the development of more effective and sustainable human resource management policies and practices.

So it can make a significant contribution to understanding the factors that influence organizational commitment among MAN teachers, as well as providing direction for the development of more effective human resource management strategies in this educational institution.

METHOD

This research uses quantitative methods with path analysis using a decomposition model [23]. The aim is to reveal the impact of leadership, organizational culture, and job satisfaction on the organizational commitment of MAN teachers in West Sumatra.

The research population consists of all MAN teachers in West Sumatra who are actively teaching in 2020/2021 and have status as Civil Servants. The number of samples to be studied is 280 people, selected through a random sampling method.

The research instrument is a questionnaire that was prepared to take into account several principles, such as avoiding questionable and abstract questions. Data was collected through distributing questionnaires to civil servant teachers who were the research samples.

Data analysis was carried out using classical assumption tests, simple and multiple linear regression analysis, hypothesis testing (t-test, F test, coefficient of determination R^2), as well as path analysis to understand the relationship between variables in more depth.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Analysis Results

a) Leadership Data Description

Based on the results of data analysis, researchers found an average score of 85, with a standard deviation of 16.228, a median of 192.50, a mode of 179, a number of classes of 9, and a class length of 9. Based on the trend distribution as depicted in Table 1.

Table 1: Frequency Distribution of Leadership Tendencies

No	Interval Class	Frequency	Relative Frequency (%)
1	140 – 148	1	0.40
2	149 – 157	0	0.00
3	158 – 166	5	1.98
4	167 – 174	43	17.06
5	175 – 183	40	15.87
6	184 - 192	37	14.68
7	193 – 201	52	20.63
8	202 - 210	41	16.27
9	211 - 255	33	13.10
	Amount	252	100.00

Based on the respondent's level of leadership achievement, it can be seen in the following Table 2.

Table 2: Level of Leadership Achievement of Respondents

No	Category	Amount	Percentage
1	Very high	58	23,02
2	Tall	120	47,62
3	Currently	73	28,97
4	Renah	1	0,40
5	Very low	0	0,00
	Amount	252	100,00

The tendency for respondents' level of achievement in the leadership variable is relatively high (47.62%).

b) Data Description Job satisfaction

Based on the results of data analysis, it was found that the average score was 51 with a standard deviation of 12.010, median 156, mode 148 number of classes 9, and length of class 6. Based on the results of these calculations, researchers developed criteria regarding job satisfaction with a distribution trend as depicted in Table 3.

Table 3: Frequency Distribution of Job Satisfaction Trends

No	Interval Class	Frequency	Relative Frequency (%)
1	134 – 139	15	5.95
2	140 – 145	22	8.73
3	146 – 151	55	21.83
4	152 – 157	45	17.86
5	158 – 163	48	19.05
6	164 – 169	23	9.13
7	170 – 175	18	7.14
8	176 – 181	16	6.35
9	182 - 185	10	3.97
	Amount	252	100.00

Based on the level of achievement of respondents, job satisfaction can be seen in Table 4.

Table 4: Respondents' level of job satisfaction

No	Category	Amount	Percentage
1	Very high	51	20,24
2	Tall	132	52,38
3	Currently	69	27,38
4	Renah	0	0,00
5	Very low	0	0,00
	Amount	252	100,00

The tendency for respondents to achieve the job satisfaction variable is relatively high (52.38%).

c) Description of Organizational Commitment Data

Based on the results of data analysis, it was found that the average score was 75 with a standard deviation of 17.689, median 127, mode 104 number of classes 9, and length of class 9. Based on the results of these calculations, researchers developed criteria regarding Organizational Commitment with a distribution tendency as depicted in Table 5.

Table 5: Frequency Distribution of Organizational Commitment Tendencies

No	Interval Class	Frequency	Relative Frequency (%)
1	95 – 103	22	8.73
2	104 – 112	45	17.86
3	113 – 121	31	12.30
4	122 – 130	51	20.24
5	131 – 139	35	13.89
6	140 – 148	42	16.67
7	149 – 157	11	4.37
8	158 – 166	11	4.37
9	167 – 170	4	1.59
	Amount	252	100.00

Based on the level of achievement of respondents, organizational commitment can be seen in Table 6.

Table 6: Respondents' Achievement Level of Organizational Commitment

No	Category	Amount	Percentage
1	Very high	18	7,14
2	Tall	49	19,44
3	Currently	76	30,16
4	Renah	109	43,25
5	Very low	0	0,00
	Amount	252	100,00

The tendency for respondents' level of achievement in the organizational commitment variable is relatively low (43.25%).

d) Testing Direct and Indirect Effects

Based on the results of the analytical calculations above, there is a direct influence of the leadership variable (X1), on the organizational commitment variable (Y), which is 4.88%, the job satisfaction variable (X2) on the organizational commitment variable (Y) is 9.79%, the variable leadership (X1) on the job satisfaction variable (X2) is 1.84%,

the leadership variable (X1) on the organizational commitment variable (Y) through the job satisfaction variable (X2) is 0.89%, and a summary table can be prepared as illustrated in Table 7.

Table 7: Summary of Analysis of Direct and Indirect Effects of Exogenous Variables on Endogenous Variables

No	Information	Direct %	Indirect %	Amount %
1	Direct influence (X1) on (Y)	4,88		
2	Indirect influence (X1) on (Y) through (X2)		0,89	
3	Direct and indirect influence (X1) on (Y)			5,77
4	Direct influence (X2) on (Y)	15,21		
7	Direct influence (X2) on (Y)			9,79
8	Influence of other variables			59,78

Based on the calculation of the results of the percentage analysis above, it is known that there is a direct and indirect influence of exogenous variables, namely leadership (X1), and organizational culture (X2), on endogenous variables, namely job satisfaction (X3) and organizational commitment (Y) as summarized below. It turns out that from the results of the study above, it can be concluded that the largest contribution that influences organizational commitment, both directly and indirectly, comes from the leadership variable (X2) to organizational commitment (Y) with an effective contribution percentage figure of 4.88%. Then, the largest contribution to two followed by the variable) job satisfaction (X2) on organizational commitment (Y) with an effective contribution percentage figure of 9.79%. Meanwhile, the influence of the organizational culture variable (X1) on organizational commitment (Y) obtained the smallest percentage figure, namely 5.77%.

Discussion

Based on the results of hypothesis testing, it is proven that leadership has a positive and significant effect on the organizational commitment of State Madrasah Aliyah teachers in West Sumatra. This positive influence shows that the better the leadership carried out, the higher the organizational commitment to the organization. This is demonstrated by always providing assistance to teachers who have worked hard, being satisfied with the salary/wages given, respecting employees who have worked hard, and always demanding that teachers prioritize carrying out their duties over other matters. The results of this research support research conducted by Raja & Palanichamy (2011) which states that leadership has a positive effect on organizational commitment [24].

Several related researchers have proven that leadership has a significant influence on organizational commitment. According to Grego-Planer (2019) in his research, he explained that the term "commitment" which is important in all organizations is closely related to the sustainability aspect of the organization. This is supported by the explanation of Zhou et al (2023) which states that leadership has an influence on triggering the formation of organizational commitment [25].

The third hypothesis which states that job satisfaction has a significant effect on organizational commitment can be accepted. This is proven through the results of the regression test which shows significant results. This means that job satisfaction has a significant influence on organizational commitment. Data on descriptive statistics also shows the mean score of the Job Satisfaction variable and the organizational commitment variable. This data supports that teacher job satisfaction will produce

good organizational commitment. The better the teacher's job satisfaction, the better the teacher's organizational commitment. Likewise, vice versa, when teachers feel less satisfied, the teacher's organizational commitment will be lower.

The results of this research are in accordance with the results of previous research examined by Bashir & Gani (2020) which found a positive influence of job satisfaction on organizational commitment [26]. These results are in accordance with the theory which states that job satisfaction is a worker's assessment of how much work can enable him to remain in the company and as a whole satisfies his needs [27]. These results show that the more satisfied employees are working at the company, the higher the employee's organizational commitment.

These studies found that there is a positive and significant influence of the job satisfaction variable on the organizational commitment variable. This research also strengthens the opinion of Brown & Sargeant (2007) who said that various studies have shown that people who are relatively satisfied with their work will be more committed to their organization [28]. Saridakis et al (2020) also stated that the strong relationship between job satisfaction and organizational commitment has been known for many years [29], this was also confirmed by Stum in Ramalho Luz et al (2018) who stated that one of the factors that influence Organizational commitment is job satisfaction [30].

Various research studies show that people who are relatively satisfied with their jobs are more committed to the organization [31]. According to Alnajjar (1996), there is a significant and positive relationship between job satisfaction and organizational commitment [32]. This research is relevant to Moorman et al (1993) that job satisfaction reflects a person's feelings towards their job, when someone is satisfied with their job they will be more committed to the organization [33]. This is in line with research by Moorman et al (1993) in several American companies stating that providing appropriate salaries and promotions will influence employees' desire to remain loyal to the organization [34]. According to Ineson et al (2013), in their research conducted at several companies in Taiwan, they stated that job satisfaction has a significant positive influence on organizational commitment [35]. Salisu et al (2015) research in the public sector in Nigeria states that employees will be more committed to providing services to consumers when they feel satisfied with their work and are given career opportunities [36].

From the results of hypothesis testing, it is proven that leadership has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. This shows that good leadership can increase job satisfaction for State Madrasah Aliyah teachers in West Sumatra. Leaders who always listen to the input given by employees in making decisions have an influence on the level of employee job satisfaction. In this case, employees are satisfied with the work they do and are responsible for their work. The results of this research support research conducted by Nazim & Mahmood (2018) which also proves that leadership has a positive relationship with job satisfaction [37]. The results of this research are also consistent with research conducted by Shahab & Nisa (2014) which also shows that leadership has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction [38].

Several studies regarding leadership and job satisfaction have been conducted previously, including by Nazim & Mahmood (2018) who stated that there is a positive and significant relationship between leadership and job satisfaction [39]. Employee job satisfaction can be created both by providing various forms of facilities and motivation

in the form of attention and support from a leader [40]. Research by Long et al (2014) states that leadership style influences employee job satisfaction [41]. This is shown in the leader's attitude which is described as a leader who is wise in determining relationships with employees, a leader who is able to communicate well, a leader who explains the details of work well, a leader who has good friendship values with subordinates, a leader who trusts employees, and a leader who has good relationships. good with employees [42]. Therefore, if a leader can show a good attitude, employee job satisfaction will increase in the work environment. Rad & Yarmohammadian (2006) in their research stated the same thing that there is a positive relationship between leadership style and employee job satisfaction [43]. Job satisfaction is a factor that encourages workers to work and is an emotional condition that is pleasant or unpleasant for employees.

CONCLUSION

The research results show that there is a direct influence between leadership and organizational commitment, as well as between job satisfaction and organizational commitment. The better the leadership, the higher the level of organizational commitment, while the lower the leadership, the lower the performance. Likewise with job satisfaction, the higher the level of job satisfaction, the higher the resulting organizational commitment, and vice versa. Apart from that, it was also found that there was a direct influence between leadership and teacher job satisfaction, where the better the leadership, the higher the teacher's job satisfaction. There is also an indirect influence, where leadership through job satisfaction contributes 20.89% to organizational commitment, indicating that through job satisfaction, teacher organizational commitment can increase significantly by 2.52%.

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